

Comparing Timbre-based Features for Musical Genre Classification

Martin Hartmann, Pasi Saari, Petri Toiviainen and Olivier Lartillot

Finnish Centre of Excellence in Interdisciplinary Music Research, Department of Music, University of Jyväskylä
[firstname].[lastname]@jyu.fi

ABSTRACT

People can accurately classify music based on its style by listening to less than half a second of audio. This has motivated efforts to build accurate predictive models of musical genre based upon short-time musical descriptions. In this context, perceptually relevant features have been considered crucial but only little research has been conducted in this direction. This study compared two timbral features for supervised classification of musical genres: 1) the Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC), coming from the speech domain and widely used for music modeling purposes; and 2) the more recent Sub-Band Flux (SBF) set of features which has been designed specifically for modeling human perception of polyphonic musical timbre. Differences in performance between models were found, suggesting that the SBF feature set is more appropriate for musical genre classification than the MFCC set. In addition, spectral fluctuations at both ends of the frequency spectrum were found to be relevant for discrimination between musical genres. The results of this study give support to the use of perceptually motivated features for musical genre classification.

Introduction

Humans are very accurate at arranging music into genre classes, even when pieces were listened for the first time. Further, the correct genre might not be known by listeners, but they could still affirm to what genres a piece of music would definitely not belong to. In fact, less than half a second of music is enough information for people to classify the type of music with great accuracy and identify other information such as title and artist [1, 2].

This brings the question of how people perceive and recognize musical styles and what are the descriptions in the music that make it possible to categorically decide that a given song belongs to a specific genre. In other words, the question is how can humans confidently build hypotheses about the style of musical pieces based on such a limited evidence. It seems that the vertical structure of the music or short-time descriptions of musical polyphonic timbre could help us to understand these fascinating perceptual

processes. However, it is not easy to build accurate predictive models of musical higher-level knowledge based on musical timbre descriptions. One reason is the lack of an acoustic explanation of polyphonic timbre. Pitch and loudness can be described as high or low, but musical timbre cannot be directly measured this way since it is possibly composed of multiple perceptual dimensions [3], such as dryness, brightness, or fullness. A second reason for this difficulty refers to the indirect path between musical descriptors and what is actually understood by humans about the musical content. In the particular case of content-based music information retrieval (MIR), this “semantic gap” refers to the insufficiency of low-level information extracted from the musical signal to arrange music based on cultural meanings and interpretations shared by communities [4]. Despite these problems, plenty of approaches to music genre classification have been suggested for more than a decade.

The aim of this study is to compare the performance of two timbre-based features for supervised music genre classification. The *mel-frequency cepstral coefficients* (MFCC) [5] come from the domain of speech and have been widely used for multiple music modeling purposes, whereas the *sub-band flux* set of features (SBF) has been recently suggested [6] and it is designed specifically for musical polyphonic timbre modeling. A main premise in this study is that perceptually relevant timbre-based features can help us understand better the acoustic foundation of polyphonic musical timbre and alleviate the constraints of the semantic gap in music genre classification. The performance of these two descriptors was comprehensively inspected using different data sets, feature combinations and learning algorithms for feature selection and classification.

1. BACKGROUND

Genre classification is widely studied in MIR perhaps because musical genres have been historically important in music stores and libraries for categorization based on essential similarities. In the digital era, automatic genre classification offers applications outside scientific areas, for example in radio playlists, music database systems or for content tagging in social networking services.

The task of genre classification has been reviewed, for example, in [7]. A great variety of musical features has been evaluated for music genre classification based on audio signal. Commonly extracted features are timbral, rhythmic and melodic [7]. The best results for this task seem to be obtained using timbre-based feature extraction. For example [8] obtained one of the highest performances for

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Feature	Frequency Range (Hz)
Sub-band No. 1	0 - 50
Sub-band No. 2	50 - 100
Sub-band No. 3	100 - 200
Sub-band No. 4	200 - 400
Sub-band No. 5	400 - 800
Sub-band No. 6	800 - 1600
Sub-band No. 7	1600 - 3200
Sub-band No. 8	3200 - 6400
Sub-band No. 9	6400 - 12800
Sub-band No. 10	12800 - 22050

Table 1: Sub-Band Flux frequency ranges.

the data sets analyzed in this study using a feature extraction method that roughly consisted of the computation of modulation spectra from timbre-based features. There has been also research on combinations based on different musical representations, for example [9] using chord transition rules together with spectral, rhythmic and melodic features. As regards the number of features used for classification, it is important to reduce the feature space of models to ease their interpretation and avoid over-fitting, which might arise e.g. due to data noise. For instance, feature selection based on genre separation ability has been implemented to evaluate timbre features for music clustering [10].

Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients

The MFCCs are widely used in plenty of MIR tasks to discard pitch information and describe the spectral shape of the musical signal. This set of features was designed in the 70s for speech recognition purposes [5] and were later implemented in music modeling [11]. Due to their widespread use, MFCCs are often selected as a timbral feature benchmark, so it is common to compare new timbre-based features against the MFCCs. For example, non-negative matrix factorization of spectrograms were introduced for genre classification and their performance was assessed against results obtained using MFCCs [12].

Sub-Band Flux

The SBF set of features is a descriptor of perceived polyphonic musical timbre and was pioneered by [6]. The set represents frequency and amplitude fluctuations as a function of time in ten octave-scaled frequency channels. High correlations between this feature set and perceptual ratings of polyphonic timbre were found in the study by [6]. 35 participants rated 100 very short musical excerpts using bipolar timbre semantic scales (Strong-Weak, Empty-Full, and so forth). Using factor analysis, the results were grouped into three perceptual dimensions: *Brightness*, *Activity* and *Fullness*. A regression analysis showed that some SBFs explained optimally these dimensions. Similar results were also found in a cross-cultural setting [13], and [14] recently found high correlations between SBFs and movement features in a study on music-induced movement.

Data Set	GTZAN	ISMIR04
Genre classes	blues (100)	classical (320)
	classical (100)	electronic (115)
	country (100)	jazz/blues (26)
	disco (100)	metal/punk (45)
	hip hop (100)	rock/pop (101)
	jazz (100)	world (122)
	metal (100)	
	pop (100)	
	reggae (100)	
	rock (100)	
Excerpts	1000	729

Table 2: Music data sets used for data collection.

Primary Set	Features
SBF _μ	10
MFCC _μ	13
SBF _{μσ}	20
MFCC _μ +SBF _μ	23
MFCC _{μσ}	26
MFCC _{μσ} +SBF _{μσ}	46

Table 3: Feature combinations used in the study and their respective sizes. Means are represented with the symbol μ and the combination of means and standard deviations is represented as $\mu\sigma$.

The SBF derives from the spectral flux feature, which is defined as the Euclidean distance between successive spectral frames. For the calculation of the SBFs, the signal is firstly decomposed with an octave-scaled filter bank using the frequency ranges shown in Table 1. The spectral flux is computed for each of the resulting frequency channels.

2. METHOD

This section will explain in detail how the feature extraction and classification stages were performed in this study. Musical features were extracted from two data sets, and the descriptors were compounded into subsets of different sizes using feature combination and dimensionality reduction. Finally, a classification stage of distribution modeling and testing was implemented. The general design is illustrated in Figure 1.

Data Sets

In order to compare both timbre-based features, two data sets were used: the GTZAN set, originally developed for one of the first studies on musical genre classification [15], and the ISMIR04 set, which is a publicly available part of a bigger data set [16]. Before being subjected to feature extraction, the musical data was preprocessed by trimming audio down to 50 seconds from the middle of each file to reduce computational load in the ISMIR04 data set, which

Figure 1: General design of the study.

consists of whole songs. Also the sampling rate was uniformed to 44100 Hz as a means to use the same algorithms for feature extraction in both data sets.

The main characteristics of the GTZAN and ISMIR04 data sets are presented in Table 2. The data sets differ in number and type of genre classes and in number of excerpts. Also the relative balance of the data sets, or the distribution of the examples into genres is fairly different. GTZAN is a balanced data set because each of the genres contains 100 musical examples. This differs from the imbalance of the ISMIR04 data set, which for example contains 320 classical songs but only 26 examples in the *jazz/blues* class.

Feature extraction

The frame-based extraction of MFCCs and SBFs was performed in MIRtoolbox 1.3 [17] using an analysis window of 25 milliseconds and a hop size of 50 % following pre-

vious studies such as [15]. Two feature statistics were obtained, the average (μ) and standard deviation (σ) along frames. In addition, a feature scaling to zero mean and unit variance was performed based upon the normality assumption. The aim of this standardization procedure was to prevent the classification results from getting distorted by the feature ranges.

The means and standard deviations of MFCCs and SBFs were combined into different feature sets to assess classification upon different scenarios. Six primary sets of different feature size were generated, as presented in Table 3.

Feature Selection and Classification

Each of the six primary sets was subjected to the attribute selection and classification stage. Pattern recognition algorithms were run in Weka, a suite for machine learning [18]. First, optimal feature subsets were obtained using feature

Figure 2: GTZAN (a) and ISMIR04 (b) accuracies as a function of feature cardinality.

selection. The final classification stage consisted of model building and testing of the subsets.

In order to perform feature selection and classification, a random division of the data into training and testing subsamples was undertaken. The music datasets were split into halves to ensure a good tradeoff between train and test data. Training data was used for the feature selection stage and for model training, whereas testing data was saved for further use in the final classification. The data splitting was stratified, i.e. a similar ratio of examples per class between training and testing sets was ensured.

The feature selection stage was performed using Wrapper forward selection algorithms. In Wrapper selection, the training set is used as a new primary set. This set is partitioned into training and testing data for the purpose of inner classification. Three algorithms were tested for feature selection using inner 4-fold CV: instance-based k -Nearest Neighbors ($k=10$) (k -NN), Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Naïve Bayes (NB). For each primary set, subsets of all possible sizes were generated. The features chosen for the subsets were the best ones for each subset size based on maximum classification rates.

Next, a model was built and tested for each of the feature subsets in a classification routine that consisted of the same learning algorithms used for feature selection. An outer CV loop was utilized to obtain final classification estimates by evaluating a maximum amount of instances. The loop consisted of a three-step sequence of random partition of the primary sets, feature selection and classification that was repeated 10 times. Finally and for each classification model, the CV accuracies were averaged.

3. RESULTS

The classification accuracy per CV split was calculated as the number of correctly classified instances divided by the total number of test music examples. A total of 828 classification estimates were obtained after averaging the accuracy values that were obtained from each cross-validation fold. The results are presented in Figures 2a and 2b, which show the classification estimates as a function of feature cardinality. Each of 18 profiles in the plots is grouped to indicate classification models using MFCCs, SBFs, or a combination of both. For both data sets, the highest accuracies were offered by the $MFCC_{\mu\sigma} + SBF_{\mu\sigma}$ feature set (SVM classification). The maximum CV accuracy obtained for the GTZAN set was 67.28 % using SVMs for classification of the best 34 features from the feature combination $MFCC_{\mu\sigma} + SBF_{\mu\sigma}$. For the ISMIR04 set, the maximum CV accuracy was 70.58 % using SVMs to classify the $MFCC_{\mu\sigma} + SBF_{\mu\sigma}$ best 36 features. The second highest accuracies were obtained using $SBF_{\mu\sigma}$ (SVM classification). For any particular feature size, classification models consisting of feature means and standard deviations ($\mu\sigma$) performed better than models with only mean (μ) feature values. As regards the learning algorithm used, the best performances of each feature combination were obtained using SVMs. The minimum CV accuracies, obtained from the $MFCC_{\mu\sigma}$ subsets of the best single feature using k -NNs, were 45.99 % in GTZAN and 22.10 % in ISMIR04.

Figure 3: Mean t -value for each feature across all pairs of genres (GTZAN).

4. ANALYSIS

The MFCCs and SBFs were compared by performing statistical analyses of difference between classification model performances and by estimating the separation ability between genre classes that was yielded by the features. Only the GTZAN data set was chosen for most of the analyses; both sets are difficult to compare due to their differences in number of excerpts and in type and distribution of genre classes. GTZAN was preferred over ISMIR04 because it is widely used in MIR; another reason is that its balanced distribution made it possible to compare SBFs and MFCCs using t -tests for equal sample sizes, thus offering a relatively higher statistical power.

The separation ability is here understood as the level of discrimination between classes obtained using independent two-sided paired t -tests. Figure 3 offers an estimation of the feature relevance for overall discrimination between genres for the GTZAN data set. The plot shows, for each feature, a mean t -value that summarizes paired t -tests for assessment of separability between each possible pair of genres in GTZAN. The lowest and uppermost SBFs as well as the MFCC σ 3 yielded high mean t -statistic values.

For further analyses based on the classification accuracies, it was relevant to estimate if the obtained performance was above chance level. The baseline accuracy [19] of a data set is used as a benchmark for this purpose. It corresponds to the percentage of the class that is most frequent in the set. For both data sets, the obtained CV accuracies were found to surpass the accuracy that would be obtained by assigning all the examples to the most populated class. The GTZAN baseline is 10 %, while the obtained minimum CV accuracy was 22.10 %. In the case of the ISMIR04 set, the baseline is 43.9 %, while the minimum result obtained was 45.99 %. Since the minimum results were higher than baseline accuracies, the obtained performance exceeded chance level.

For the next analyses based upon classification results it was opted to utilize models based on the SVM learning algorithm. Only this classification technique was chosen because for each of the classifiers that were tested, the difference between the performance of MFCC and SBF models was found to be fairly similar.

The results of all the SVM classifications based on full-sized feature combinations were compared in order to find out whether the performance of MFCC and SBF models differed. Since the number of cross-validation folds was not large enough to meet normality assumption [19], the accuracies obtained for each full-sized feature combination were assessed running a non-parametric Friedman's test with post-hoc analysis following previous studies such as [20]. Figures 4a and 4b show the differences in performance between the classification models. Each box plot displays the per-fold performance distribution of a single feature combination. The figures show eleven differences between models at p -values lower than 0.05, out of which three were found for both GTZAN and ISMIR04 models: 1) The $\text{SBF}_{\mu\sigma}$ set performed higher than the MFCC_{μ} set at $p < .001$ level; 2) the MFCC_{μ} set yielded lower results than the $\text{MFCC}_{\mu\sigma} + \text{SBF}_{\mu\sigma}$ feature set ($p < .001$); 3) the $\text{MFCC}_{\mu\sigma} + \text{SBF}_{\mu\sigma}$ feature set performed higher than the feature combination $\text{MFCC}_{\mu\sigma}$ (ISMIR04: $p < .001$, GTZAN: $p < .05$).

Finally, an analysis based on SVM classification results obtained from full sized combinations of $\text{MFCC}_{\mu\sigma}$ and of $\text{SBF}_{\mu\sigma}$ was carried out for the GTZAN set data. These particular classification models were chosen in order to compare all the SBF descriptors against the totality of the extracted MFCC descriptors. The most accurately classified genres for the chosen models were classical, metal and jazz.

The $\text{MFCC}_{\mu\sigma}$ and $\text{SBF}_{\mu\sigma}$ models were compared by finding out if there were any genres for which one fea-

Figure 4: Comparison of SVM classification results based on different feature set combinations using GTZAN (a) and ISMIR04 (b) music data sets. The boxes are presented in increasing order of median classification accuracy. A Friedman’s test was utilized to find differences based on the CV accuracies of each full-sized feature set combination. Differences in performance of classification model pairs that exhibited p-values lower than 0.05 are shown with braces. The corresponding p-values for these cases are indicated with asterisks (*: $p < .05$, **: $p < .01$, ***: $p < .001$).

ture combination offered good class separability but the other did not, and vice versa. The separability between classes was evaluated from the t -statistic of all the features for certain pairs of genres. The genre pairs shown in Figure 5 were chosen based upon the $MFCC_{\mu\sigma}$ and the $SBF_{\mu\sigma}$ SVM classification models and their differences in genre misclassification. In order to find the genre pairs, the confusion matrices corresponding to these classification models were modified by summing their respective upper and lower triangles in order to add the false positives of each possible genre pair together. Two triangular matrices were obtained; the triangle corresponding to $SBF_{\mu\sigma}$ was subtracted from the $MFCC_{\mu\sigma}$ triangle, and vice versa. The required genre pairs were chosen from the elements in the triangular matrices based on the maximum values that were obtained from each subtraction. It was found that country and jazz were relatively highly misclassified by $SBF_{\mu\sigma}$ models and relatively lowly by $MFCC_{\mu\sigma}$ models: as shown in Figure 5, the $MFCC_{\sigma 3}$ descriptor showed a comparatively high t -statistic with regards to the separability between country and jazz. In contrast, hip-hop and reggae showed relatively high misclassification for $MFCC_{\mu\sigma}$ and comparatively low for $SBF_{\mu\sigma}$ models. As shown in the plot, the $SBF_{\sigma 3}$ offered the highest t -values for the discrimination of these genres. A similar procedure with symmeterized confusion matrices was used in a genre classification study by [20].

5. DISCUSSION

The comparisons between the MFCC and SBF sets over different conditions showed that SBF sets performed better than MFCCs in the majority of the cases. This is observed for both music data sets despite variations in the general shape of the GTZAN and ISMIR04 plots (Figs. 4a and 4b) that might be due to differences in their baseline accuracies. To illustrate this, classical music comprises 10 % of the balanced GTZAN data set, which has 10 classes. In comparison, from the unbalanced ISMIR04 set with 6 classes, almost 44 % consists of classical music. This genre is in the latter case overrepresented, which would lead to relatively higher results in ISMIR04 if a naïve learner assigned all the examples to the most populated class.

As regards the use of different learning algorithms to find differences between MFCC and SBF model performance, it was found that the results were consistent for the three classifiers used. It can be suggested that the difference in performance between SBF and MFCC models is mostly invariant, at least with respect to the chosen classifiers.

Based on the analysis of mean separability, congruent results were found between the class discrimination obtained from certain features and prior findings regarding perceived polyphonic timbre dimensions. As shown in Figure 3, the mean separability of each feature for all possible combinations of genres yields fairly different profiles for MFCCs and SBFs, probably because the features themselves are fundamentally different. The high average t -statistic for the extreme SBFs suggests that the lower and

Figure 5: T -statistic of all features in genre pairs (country/pop in upper graph, hip hop/reggae in lower graph) for which $MFCC_{\mu\sigma}$ and $SBF_{\mu\sigma}$ models showed important differences in genre misclassification (GTZAN data set).

upper extremes of the spectrum are especially important for the purpose of genre classification. This tendency follows results by [6, 13] regarding correlations between SBFs from the extreme frequency channels and the perception of polyphonic timbral Activity, Fullness and Brightness. Indeed, the SBF descriptors with the highest t -values in Figure 3 were found to correlate with perceptual dimensions in previous studies on polyphonic timbre perception [6]. It can be thus suggested that the perceived dimensions of Activity, Fullness and Brightness that are described by some SBFs are relevant for the purpose of musical genre classification. In this sense, perceptually motivated features have been considered potentially crucial for music classification [21], although few research has been conducted so far in this direction.

The aforementioned contemplation might be also valid for some MFCC descriptors, particularly $MFCC_{\mu 1}$ and $MFCC_{\sigma 3}$. The relevance of perceived brightness is also suggested by the high average t -value of $MFCC_{\mu 1}$, which correlates with this timbral feature. As regards $MFCC_{\sigma 3}$, which corresponds to energy at extreme low and mid-high frequencies, this descriptor exhibited a high mean t -statistic, implying that the lower spectrum end might be purposeful for genre classification. Based on the cosine basis function corresponding to $MFCC_3$, inter-class discriminations from this feature correspond to differences in energy covariance between the lower extreme of the mel spectrum and frequencies around 2500 Hz.

The $MFCC_{\sigma 3}$ was also found to discriminate well jazz music from country, as shown in Figure 5. Since this feature is a standard deviation, it is plausible that the separability obtained between jazz and country is due to a relatively higher variance in low frequencies over time in the

case of country music. As regards the discrimination between hip hop and reggae, the t -test results in Figure 5 showed that this appears to be a burdensome task using MFCCs. The SBFs that can separate better these two classes are the means and standard deviations of SBF 3 and SBF 4, which correspond to fluctuations at low frequencies. Perhaps the generally “fuller” sound that could be perceived in hip hop music when compared to reggae corresponds to the higher SBF $\mu 3$ found in hip hop excerpts, as SBF 2 and SBF 3 represent perceived Fullness [6, 13].

Notably, standard deviations of features not only offered particularly good separability but also seemed to be favorable with regards to the obtained classification performance when compared to feature combinations that consisted only of mean values. With this respect, it might be that the addition of standard deviations increased the feature redundancy of the subsets, reducing its noise and improving the separation between classes [22]. In any case, the results raised the question of the relevance of standard deviations for music classification. While the feature means are a customary measure of central tendency, the feature standard deviations are less prevalent and could be considered as a problematic statistic for music description. These refer to changes over time, but do not give cues about the temporal evolution of the music because the time-scale of change is unknown. To illustrate this, the loudness of a musical piece that is *pp* during the first half and *ff* during the second half could have the same standard deviation as that of a piece whose dynamics varied periodically.

It is worthy to remark that the separability analyses were conducted for individual features and for pairs of genre classes, thus it is not possible to tell whether the features that yielded high t -values had an optimal individual contribution in the multi-class classification experiment with multiple features. In other words, descriptors that showed high separation ability might not have necessarily been decisive in the classification task.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The present findings showed that the SBF feature set, which has been designed specifically for modeling human perception of polyphonic musical timbre, is a promising feature for genre classification due to its satisfactory classification performance over a number of scenarios. For the analyzed cases, SBF models performed better than MFCC models. In addition, spectral fluctuations at both ends of the frequency spectrum were found to be relevant for discrimination between musical genres. Even though the classification results were comparatively lower than those obtained by other approaches using a higher number of features and pioneering classification methods, the outcomes of this study encourage the evaluation of perceptually motivated features for musical genre classification. The results follow previous ideas regarding the importance of global frequency distribution in genre discrimination [4], and support the hypothesis that the energy fluctuations within certain frequency channels, more specifically in lower and upper spectrum ends, can be very useful for the task of

music genre classification. A possible extension of the presented work would be to test the SBF feature set in other MIR tasks such as music segmentation. Other natural directions for future studies in genre classification include the use of SBF with newer modeling techniques as well as experiments on more challenging music data sets. Finally, the design of perceptually interpretable features that boost efficiency through compact musical representations can provide critical insights for MIR.

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